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Abednego Chibuzo Kanu ^{1*}, Abdulrasaq O. Akanbi ¹, Ridwan Enuwa Mohammed ¹, Aishat A. Yusuf ¹, Wasiu O. Yahaya ¹, Owoicho Ogwuche ¹ & Jummai Jerry ²

¹ Department of Science Education
Faculty of Education,
University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

² Department of Special Education,
Nasarawa State University, Keffi,
Nasarawa State, Nigeria

*Correspondence: kanu.ac@unilorin.edu.ng; ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-8256-2864> (ACK)

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Abstract: *Students with disabilities in the sub-Saharan African region have experienced bottlenecks in accessing STEM education. The position paper explored the effectiveness of multi-sensory stimulation strategies as a panacea to the quagmire faced by students with disabilities and for their enhanced STEM education performance in the region. The paper argued that for inclusivity and quality education to be actualized as contained in the Goal-4 target of the United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the interests of students with disabilities as it concerns STEM education must be considered for improvement. Spotlight was beamed on the condition of students with disabilities and STEM education in the region highlighting the challenges of continuing the use of conventional teaching methods for instructional delivery amidst learners with divergent needs. Among other innovative teaching-learning strategies, multi-sensory stimulation strategies were examined with the theoretical framework primarily hinged on Dual Coding Theory proposed by Allan Paivio in 1971. Implications for multimedia learning were synthesized and common multi-sensory stimulation strategies highlighted. Searchlight was beamed on the benefits and challenges with the implementation. The paper concluded with suggestions for effective implementation of the strategies for the good of students with disabilities in the sub-Saharan African clime. Among others, the suggestions include the need to install assistive technologies such as screen readers, braille displays and specialized keyboards in mobile devices and computers to enable students with disabilities participate fully in multi-sensory learning. Also, in-service training and workshops on multi-sensory approaches should be provided alongside mentorship programmes and peer support networks for teachers.*

Key words: Multi-sensory stimulation strategies, STEM education, Students with disabilities, Nigerian educational setting

Introduction

Essential provisions of the Goal-4 target of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) include entrenching quality education for all, reducing disparities in education and making education a lifelong enterprise. These noble ideals being projected are in terms of access and in terms of quality (United Nations' International Children's Emergency Fund/ UNICEF, 2024). Inclusive in this noble target-4 of the SDGs is the incorporation and assurance of equal access to all levels of education and vocational training for the vulnerable, including persons with disabilities and the elimination of gender disparities (UNESCO, 2021). Strategies meant to improve learning outcomes amongst learners with disabilities are part of the measures to achieve this United Nations' target, emphasizing the dire need for inclusive education that caters for variegated needs. The need to provide and ensure accessible learning environments, motivated trained educators and tailored support cannot be under-estimated, more so, to enable learners with disabilities attain their full potential and achieve high quality education (Jerry & Kanu, 2025). This position paper provides advocacy for the effectiveness of multi-sensory stimulation strategies in the Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education of students with disabilities in sub-Saharan African nations such as Nigeria; also highlights best practices, challenges and suggestions for educators and policy-makers. Multi-sensory stimulation strategies have been shown to significantly enhance learning outcomes for students with disabilities in various educational settings of other climes in the contexts of STEM education (Taljaard, 2016). These strategies could be explored and harnessed for enhanced academic performance of students with disabilities in the sub-Saharan Africa.

On instructional delivery of STEM to learners including students with disabilities in sub-Saharan Africa clime, certain innovative teaching-learning strategies have been projected. These innovative strategies, according to Anikweze and Kanu (2025) include peer-mediated instruction, gamification and simulations, project-based learning, community-based learning, mobile learning and multi-sensory stimulation. Others abound such as universal design for learning and assistive technology integration (Zajgar & Dobraca, 2025). Each of these novel instructional delivery strategies for students with disabilities in STEM education has its merits and demerits. For instance, an inclusive learning environment could be created by training peers to support students with disabilities as well as deploying interactive immersive experiences that simplify complex STEM concepts and principles. Tools such as text-to-speech software, adaptive laboratory equipment and graphic organizers could be utilized to enhance accessibility for the physically challenged students (Ekpete & Blessing, 2025). Multi-sensory stimulation strategies are particularly being advocated for in this paper for diverse learners including those with disabilities. Effectiveness and other cogent reasons have been adduced. By engaging multiple senses at the same time, inclusive learning could be enhanced catering for different learning styles and abilities and beneficial to students with disabilities (Romano & Latino, 2025). Preferences of multi-sensory stimulation over other strategies are based on potential for enhanced retention of learning experiences, adaptable to local contexts/ cultures, being accessible and amenable to connect abstract concepts to real-world applications with capacity to foster deeper understanding (Kanu & Agu, 2020). Educators and clinicians have for long period believed that multisensory training have capability to improve learning experiences and outcomes.

A simple benefit of multisensory stimulation strategies according to Shams and Seitz (2015) is the capacity to engage individual learner with variegated learning styles, for example, while some persons are 'visual learners'; others are 'auditory learners'. Senses such as tactile, olfactory and taste could be used for wider range of learners including the physically challenged learners to understand lessons and concepts in the classroom (MikeChin, 2011). Multi-sensory training is found to be more

effective at an individualized instruction level thereby giving credence to an observation made by Treichler as observed by Shams and Seitz (2015) that 'People majorly remember 10% of what is read, 20% of what is heard, 30% of what is seen and 50% of what is seen and heard'. Many subject specialties in Montessori schools use a medley of auditory, visual, kinesthetic and tactile techniques and could be applied in STEM education of students with disabilities. This has potential to improve learning outcomes and make learning process pleasurable. In the last three decades, several novel language instruction approaches have metamorphosed into multisensory structural language education, which make use of auditory, visual, tactile-kinesthetic and articulatory methodologies for teaching-learning (Shams & Seitz, 2015).

Concerning enhanced STEM learning outcomes among students with disabilities in Nigerian educational landscape, considerations border on increased students' engagement/ interests, better grades/ test scores, improved problem-solving skills and higher number of students with disabilities pursuing STEM career opportunities. As posited by Zajgar and Dobraca (2025) this means creating inclusive and accessible learning environment consisting of materials adapted for diverse needs and assistive technologies such as audio descriptions, braille, screen readers and adaptive tools. Peer support and collaboration are encouraged alongside the training of teachers in inclusive education (Wangila & Fedha, 2025). Students with disabilities in Nigeria are faced with challenges ranging from limited accessibility in schools to stigma and insufficient resources for accommodation (Oginni, et al., 2025). Policy support for inclusive STEM education is obviously inadequate. Teacher training on disability awareness is still low and useful partnership for accessible resources on the educational needs of the physically challenged scarce (Ekpete & Blessing, 2025). Given these considerations, creating an inclusive STEM education environment cannot be undervalued for students with disabilities in Nigeria. In this paper, students with disabilities and STEM education are x-rayed highlighting the challenges they face under conventional teaching methods. Framework on which the study is hinged, working pattern, materials and types of multi-sensory stimulation strategies were discussed in relation to STEM education of students with disabilities. Suggestions for improvement were made.

STEM Education and Students with Disabilities in Sub-Saharan Africa

Students with disabilities according to Romano and Latino (2025) are individual learners who have a kind of impairments whether physical, sensory, cognitive or mental that might affect the individual's interactions with the environment or limit the person's participation in certain activities. These ones require some form of support for ease of accessing education equally (Zajgar & Dobraca, 2025). Disabilities manifest in different forms. Disabilities that affect mobility and dexterity are physical. The type that affects visual and hearing processes is sensory. The type that affects learning, for example reading fluency, decoding words, writing, spelling skills and grammar is dyslexia (Sohn, 2024). Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is cognitive impairment that affects attention, impulse control and hyperactivity (Yacoub et al., 2025). Another type of disabilities manifests in form of mental health conditions. Mental health condition has capacity of impacting students' learning and interactions through anxiety disorders, depression, bipolar disorder and post-traumatic stress disorder (Romano & Latino, 2025). Such mental health conditions are capable of interfering with the learner's concentration, emotional stability, social interaction, time management and organizational abilities (Ekpete & Blessing, 2025). To foster sustainable development and promote educational equity, inclusive STEM education must seek to provide learning opportunities regardless of gender, socio-economic background and disability status (Oginni et al., 2025).

Despite the importance of STEM education to the economic emancipation and social mobility of

the sub-Saharan African nations, excluding students with disabilities in its opportunities could perpetuate inequality capable of limiting development potential in the region (Ayeni et al., 2024). In many sub-Saharan African nations such as Nigeria, students with disabilities encounter obstacles in accessing STEM education. Manifestations of these hindrances include lack of adaptive technologies such as assistive software, screen readers, braille display materials, wheelchairs coupled with inaccessible infrastructure and limited support from educators and policymakers (Wangila & Fedha, 2025). Public structures and educational institutions are built without any consideration for the physically challenged students, for instance, doorways are narrow in some public structures and no ramps nor elevators installed in some cases. Another problem faced by students with disabilities in some African cultures is societal stigma which leads to exclusion or marginalization. Inclusive infrastructure in form of accessible schools and adaptive technologies need to be institutionalized and policies that promote inclusive education implemented by governments and schools. The importance of training and re-training for teachers on supporting students with disabilities should be emphasized. Awareness about disabilities and promotion of inclusion could be intensified through community engagement as means of reducing stigma and encouraging more physically challenged members to participate in STEM education (Ayeni et al., 2024). Organizations, governments and schools could collaborate to provide resources, expertise and support for inclusive STEM education.

Challenges faced by Students with Disabilities Under Conventional Instructional Delivery Approach in STEM Education

Challenges encountered by students with disabilities in STEM education are variegated and capable of limiting their full engagement with STEM subjects and hindering them from attaining their full potential (Wangila & Fedha, 2025). Learning materials might not be available in formats that are easily accessible to students with visual and other physical impairments; and online resources might not be compatible with assistive technologies such as screen readers, prosthetic devices or braille displays (Zajgar & Dobraca, 2025). Unavailability of certain support services such as sign language interpreters hinders students' ability to participate in STEM lessons. Laboratory equipment and workstations are often inaccessible to students with mobility impairments thereby limiting their participation in hands-on experience (Jerry & Kanu, 2025). Due to the problem of stigmatization and marginalization in the class, students with disabilities often feel excluded which affects their self-esteem and motivation. Peers and teachers sometimes have biases and low expectations of these ones which tend to affect the students' opportunities and experiences (Jerry & Kanu, 2025). Traditional assessment methods such as timed examinations accommodate students with disabilities and potentially affect their academic performance/ learning outcomes. Alternative assessment methods such as oral examinations and other adaptive formats are not often readily available nor consistently applied, if available (Ayeni et al., 2024). Challenges highlighted and others not mentioned could seriously create barriers to STEM education for the physically challenged students.

Multi-sensory Stimulation in comparison with Sensory Stimulation

Multi-sensory stimulation is sometimes used interchangeably with sensory stimulation by some educators but there are subtle differences even though in practice both approaches could be combined to create engaging and effective learning experiences. Sensory stimulation refers to the activation of one or more senses to elicit a response or promote learning (Kanu & Ohize, 2020). It involves the exploration of stimuli such as auditory, visual, olfactory, tactile, taste, gustatory and kinesthetic stimulation (Lykkeslet et al., 2014). A single sense or multiple senses might be involved with the focus being the stimulation of the senses to facilitate learning. On the other hand, multi-sensory stimulation

involves the simultaneous activation of multiple senses to create a deeper and more immersive and integrated learning experiences at a time (Morin & Wilson, 2015). It aims at engaging multiple pathways in the brain to enhance perception, retention and recall (Tinga et al., 2015). Examples of multi-sensory approaches being advocated for inclusive learning situation and meant to take care of different learning styles and abilities include visual, auditory, tactile and kinesthetic techniques (Ektepe & Blessing, 2025). Ultimately, this measure if embraced, would promote academic performance and social inclusion particularly as it affects learners with disabilities.

Frameworks for Multi-sensory Stimulation Strategies

Some frameworks have helped to structure research work and practices on multi-sensory stimulation strategies. Under conceptual framework, universal design for learning has emphasized the adoption of flexible and inclusive approaches aimed at engaging diverse learners including learners with disabilities. Also, multimedia learning theory has enabled the use of multimedia elements to support learning (Ramlatchan, 2024). Human beings have five basic senses: sense of sight, sense of touch, sense of smell, sense of hearing and sense of taste. It is worthy of mention that every sense could be used for learning purposes. For instance, the sense of sight is used in reading information, looking at text, pictures, etc. The hearing sense is used to listen to what the teacher has to say. It is common in a typical classroom situation to use only the visual and auditory senses. It has been witnessed that when a child explores an object for the first time, repeated observation of the object from different perspective and angles is combined with coordinated tactile exploration using the hands and sometimes the mouth to make the experience rewarding. Such experience is used to build up congruent association between visual and tactile stimulation (McGraw et al., 2008). The use of multiple sense organs allows for more cognitive connections and associations with a concept (Pitts, 2012). Information can easily be accessed, triggered and retrieved from learners' cognitive learning centre using multi-sensory stimulation, also makes learning pleasurable (Ramlatchan, 2024).

Theoretical Framework

The multi-sensory stimulation strategies being popularized could be hinged on the Cognitive Load Theory that guides the design of instructional materials towards managing cognitive load and then the Dual Coding Theory. This discourse took stand for the Dual Coding Theory as proposed by Allan Paivio in 1971 with some implications for multimedia learning as being explored. This theory, according to Dwi Susanti et al. (2025), suggests that the brain processes information via two separate pathways: verbal or language-based and non-verbal or image-based. The two distinct channels process, combine and connect visual and auditory information, visuals and text/audio, visual and verbal representations for strengthening understanding and enhanced learning (Li et al., 2022). Verbal channel processes information in language-based format such as text and speech; while non-verbal channel processes information in an image-based format such as pictures, diagrams and videos (Tinga et al., 2015). When information is presented in both pathways, multiple representation is created in working memory.

The implications for multimedia learning as opined by the Dual Coding Theory is the aid to comprehension and enhanced learning using images, diagrams and texts as well as improvement to retention through the combining of visuals with spoken explanations (Dwi Susanti et al., 2025). Complex concepts are clarified, transfer of information to long-term memory is enabled and retrieval/recall is easier and enhanced. In teaching, visuals are used to support text-based information, spoken explanations combined with images or diagrams and multimedia elements could be incorporated to engage learners. In treatment and recovery of patient with neurocognitive disorder in nursing homes,

multi-sensory intervention becomes a behavioural therapy used to provide divergent sensory experiences that stimulate the person's senses, perception and sensory integration (Garrido-Pedrosa et al., 2024).

The Multi-sensory stimulation teaching-learning theory states that learning can be improved upon when a teacher incorporates more than visual and auditory senses (MikeChin, 2011). The theory was propounded by Laird in 1985 (Dunn, 2002), an offshoot from the work of the German physicist, Hermann von Helmholtz, who was the first to work on sensory perception and inference (McGraw et al., 2008). The sensory stimulation theory is an idea affirmed by the scientific community and used in schools where some of the students have sensory deficit and or need different avenues for learning. Laird observed that most knowledge held by adults (about 75%) is acquired through sense of sight. Hearing is the next in effectiveness (approximately 13%) and the other senses - smell, touch and taste sums up to 12% of knowledge possessed by people. Stimulation of senses is achieved using greater variety of colours, volume levels, strong statements, facts presented in visual form and the use of a variety of techniques and media (Dunn, 2002). It was observed by Garrido-Pedrosa et al. (2024) that motivation to learn in one's daily life's activities depends extensively on the senses of perception. Cognitive psychologists recommend that the major ingredient of the intellectual process is sensory stimulation which allows human beings to be conscious of their environment through the senses and respond towards it.

Learning Materials and Working Pattern of Multi-sensory Teaching-learning

Students learn using the five basic senses and the educational resources/ materials being used vary by age and lesson subject-matter. Therefore, the teacher needs to make use of creative and imaginative abilities to find materials covering all the senses (MikeChin, 2011). Some learners are more tactile in their learning style than primarily auditory or visual, etc. As an illustration, MikeChin observed that segmented chocolate bars are good materials for teaching-learning of fractions using all five senses if the children or pupils are promised and permitted to eat the chocolate bars at the end of the lesson. The use of concept mapping for teaching, for instance, ensures effective multi-sensory stimulation of learners. Similarly, use of computer-assisted instruction and teaching machines such as tape-recorded lesson or video-taped lesson all help to enhance learning by effectively stimulating multiple senses.

Though the student or pupil might not use all the senses in every lesson (i.e. taste, touch, sight, smell, hearing and movement), the learner might engage with the learning material/resources in more than one way (McGraw et al., 2008). Multisensory teaching-learning could pass information through channels such as sight, hearing, touch and movement, otherwise referred to as tactile and kinesthetic system (Dwi Susanti et al. 2025). Some multisensory approach programmes have been developed to help learners with disabilities. These types of programmes use sight, sound, movement and touch to help children and the disadvantaged group connect language to words in a reading lesson. For example, colour-coded tiles could be used to help learners in this category connect sounds to letters. Playing tapes that involve "identifying and labeling" gives learners with disabilities the chance to develop a holistic concept. Playing soft and calming music when certain work is on could facilitate concentration. Sound could aid comprehension. Tasting and making dishes are fun activities for these learners and could make learning memorable. For example, baking is a group activity that has capacity to reinforce team spirit and co-operation in learners with disabilities (Pitt, 2012).

Multi-sensory instruction could be deployed to teach different subjects (Ramlatchan, 2024). For instance, Mathematics programmes have developed the use of manipulative tools such as interlocking

cubes, shaped blocks and small objects for teaching-learning. In science laboratories and technology workshops, students carry out different experiments and practical work, they report their observations and findings and possibly carry out analysis. Students are given the chance to create ideas and experiment themselves through touching, manipulating, making and movement. Tactile has to do with use of sense of touch and kinetic has to do with sense of movement. This scientific process sums up to multi-sensory learning experience and makes learning a fun. Pupils or students with disabilities learn better if something is placed in their front which they can feel and physically touch and if possible something they participated in setting up (Pitt, 2012).

Common Multi-sensory Stimulation Strategies and Their Differences

Popular multi-sensory stimulation strategies according to Tinga et al. (2015), Garrido-Pedrosa et al. (2024) and Dwi Susanti et al. (2025) include the following:

- (a) Visual strategies which are divers and classified as images, for example diagrams, charts and videos to convey information. Others are graphics, for instance, graphic organizers, mind maps and concept maps; and colour-coding to highlight important information.
- (b) Auditory strategies which are categorized under lectures, discussions and audio recordings; music, sound effects and voice modulation; and audio descriptions and text-to-speech software.
- (c) Tactile strategies which are grouped under hands-on activities, experiments and manipulatives; Simulations and role-playing; braille and tactile graphics for visually impaired students.
- (d) Kinesthetic strategies which are categorized into: movement-based activities, gestures and dance; physical demonstrations and experiments; building and constructing models or prototypes.
- (e) Olfactory strategies which make use of scents and aromas to enhance learning as the case in chemistry and biology practical lessons as well as the association of smells with memories and concepts.
- (f) Gustatory strategies which use taste and food to enhance learning as the case in chemistry, home management, food science and nutrition lessons respectively

Vital differences among the mentioned strategies manifest in form of uni-sensory versus multi-sensory (either focusing on one sense or combining multiple senses), intensity and duration (with some strategies being prolonged and others being brief/ subtle), level of engagement (passive to active) and cognitive load differential (with some strategies imposing higher cognitive load and others being more straightforward).

The Concept of STEM Education

STEM education is an interdisciplinary approach to the teaching-learning of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) subjects in an integrated hands-on and real-world context (Aina, 2022). It revolves around problem-solving, inquiry-based learning, projects, critical thinking and creativity alongside collaboration and team work. Ajemba (2024) pointed out that STEM education is targeted towards preparing students for high demanding job opportunities using critical thinking and collaboration and encouraging innovation and entrepreneurship. By way of contrast, whereas traditional education is subject-focused, theoretical with skills based on content knowledge,

STEM education is interdisciplinary, hands-on, project-based with skills hinged on problem-solving and critical thinking (Aina, 2022). If STEM education is adequately supported and promoted in Nigeria, the expectations of economic growth, technological advancement and students' readiness for global competitiveness and opportunities would be enhanced. Problems militating against the implementation of STEM education in Nigeria revolves around poor funding, low research output, scarcity of science teachers, infrastructural deficit, inadequate instructional resources, insecurity, corruption and brain-drain (Ajemba, 2024).

Potential Benefits of Integrating Multi-sensory stimulation strategies in STEM Education of Students with Disabilities

In the context of STEM education, multi-sensory stimulation strategies have capacity to make abstract concepts more accessible and engaging for learners with diverse needs (Kanu & Agu, 2020). In sub-Saharan Africa where resources and infrastructure are limited, leveraging multi-sensory stimulation strategies could be cost-effective and an innovative approach to improve STEM education outcomes amongst learners with disabilities. Educators have capacities to create inclusive learning environments that could cater for different learning styles and abilities, ultimately promoting academic achievement and social inclusion.

All categories of learners can benefit from multisensory instruction including learners who do not have learning and attention problems and those with disabilities (Morin & Wilson, 2015). When a student learns something with more than one sense perception, information or knowledge is likely to be impactful, meaningful and lasting in memory. Multisensory learning is particularly helpful in teaching learners with learning and attention difficulties. Such learners are availed greater opportunities and diversified ways of learning a subject. Benefits of sensory stimulation learning approach to the student and or recuperating neuro patient according to Ramlatchan (2024), Garrido-Pedrosa et al. (2024) and Dwi Susanti et al. (2025) include the following:

- i. Sensory stimulation helps the student or patient increase concentration and focus attention on the subject-matter being learnt;
- ii. It helps to develop or reactivate patient's senses of hearing, sight, smell, touch and taste;
- iii. It re-awakens awareness and improves alertness;
- iv. It improves coordination and motor development;
- v. Sensory stimulation promotes cognitive development by increased brain function;
- vi. It leads the learners to explore the processes, the materials and the concepts of their environment;
- vii. It develops a sense of cause and effect; and
- viii. It promotes communication, sharing and social interactions.

If a student learns something, adopting more than one sense perception, the information or experience is more likely to stay longer in the sub-conscious system of the student before being forgotten. This could be of help to learners with attention issues. For example, children who have challenge with visual or auditory processing might have difficulties learning through reading or

listening only. Multi-sensory teaching-learning approach is a type of hands-on learning and gives children more ways to connect new information with what they know already; understand and work through problems and inculcates non-verbal problem-solving skills in them (McGraw et al., 2008). Multi-sensory teaching helps students explore into their learning capabilities to be able to make connections and form memories. Multi-sensory teaching takes into consideration that different learners learn in different ways, thus providing multiple ways to learn which consequently gives every child a chance to excel (Morin & Wilson, 2015). Terminologies such as sensory stimulation, multi-sensory stimulation and multi-sensory environment have been sampled and applied tentatively to stimulate the senses (Lykkeslet et al., 2014). These terms were found useful in increasing alertness, reducing agitation and improving meta-cognitive ability.

Challenges of implementing Multi-sensory Stimulation Strategies in Sub-Saharan Africa

The expectations of inclusive and effective learning experiences using multi-sensory stimulation strategies for students with disabilities in sub-Saharan African setting could be hampered by some bottlenecks. These challenges, according to Suryaratri et al. (2019), Manja et al. (2024); and, Ekpete and Blessing (2025) include the following:

1. Constraints of funding, infrastructure and educational resources such as laboratory equipment, textbooks and digital tools necessary for multi-sensory learning;
2. difficulty with managing and engaging large group of students (large class size/ overcrowded classrooms), making individualized attention and engagement challenging;
3. workable strategies to adapt with and accommodate diverse languages and cultural backgrounds are herculean for the sake of inclusivity and relevance;
4. limited professional development opportunities for teachers to learn multi-sensory stimulation approaches and lack of experience hinder effective implementation;
5. Inadequate classrooms, erratic power supply and limited internet connectivity obstruct the use of technology and multi-media resources essential for multi-sensory learning; and
6. Challenges associated with assessing and evaluating students in multi-sensory environment demands innovative approach which is not easy to implement.

The constraints outlined above call for creative, context-specific solutions, collaboration and investment in education infrastructure to support effective multi-sensory learning in sub-Saharan Africa as Nigeria.

Conclusion

The integration of multi-sensory stimulation strategies in STEM instructional delivery has shown promise to improve and sustain learning experiences and performance of students with disabilities in sub-Saharan Africa. Incorporating visual, auditory, kinesthetic and other sensory stimulation strategies during teaching-learning could be a panacea for different learning needs thereby promoting inclusivity and more equitable learning environment. As Africa continues with investment in inclusive education, leveraging on multi-sensory strategies has potential to play pivotal role in empowering students with disabilities to thrive in STEM field. They would contribute meaningfully to

the socio-economic advancement of the region and global competitiveness with a positive self-concept/proud self-mage. Certain challenges with implementing multi-sensory strategies for STEM education as it concerns the physically challenged students could be tackled and surmounted if the stakeholders in the education industry collaborate to do the needful as suggested.

Suggestions for Effective Implementation of Multi-sensory Stimulation Strategies for Benefit of Learners with Disabilities in Africa

To ensure effective implementation of multi-sensory stimulation strategies in Africa, especially Nigeria for the benefit of the physically challenged students, it has become an imperative for educators to leverage open educational resources and low-cost materials that are adaptable to accommodate different abilities. Text-to-speech software for visually impaired students or sign language interpretation/ audio descriptions for hearing-impaired students and closed captions should be accessed and in partnership with organizations that support resource. Community involvement and local resource development should be encouraged as well as implementation of peer-to-peer learning and group work. Assistive technology such as screen readers, braille displays and specialized keyboards should be installed in mobile devices and computers to enable students with disabilities participate fully in multi-sensory learning. Educational apps and online platforms to facilitate engagement should be utilized with focus on key concepts and support of mobile technology/ networks widely used in Africa. Multi-sensory approaches should be tailored to individual student's needs, to allow students to learn at their own respective pace and ways that suits their abilities.

Furthermore, in-service training and workshops on multi-sensory approaches should be provided alongside the development of mentorship programmes and peer support networks for teachers leveraging online courses and resources for professional advancement. Alternative energy sources such as solar and other renewable sources should be explored while mobile devices and online digital tools are utilized in partnerships with organizations that support infrastructure development. In terms of assessment procedure, adapted assessments and evaluations should ensure equal opportunities for students with disabilities to demonstrate their knowledge and skills. Competency-based assessment and project-based evaluations should be developed leveraging technology for efficient feedback with focus on continuous, formative assessment rather than summative examinations. For the Nigerian educational environment, local cultural practices and traditions should be incorporated into teaching approaches as well as the development of community-based education initiatives and partnerships. Physically challenged students should be empowered for independence and confidence in preparation for future careers in STEM fields with the help of technology and multi-sensory approaches being advocated.

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